

The Application of The Principles of Universal Design for Learning in Teaching Students with Learning Disabilities by General Education Teachers

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: October 01, 2024</p> <p>Accepted: January 02, 2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Students With Learning Disabilities, Universal Instructional Design, General Education Teachers</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14588689</p>	<p><i>The current study aimed to identify the degree of the regular classes teachers' use of the Universal Design For Learning (UDL) principles in teaching and evaluating students with learning disabilities, as moderated by gender, experiences, and qualification variables. The researcher has followed the survey descriptive approach design. The authors have constructed a questionnaire as a data collection tool. The tool was administered on 500 male and female teachers in the Eastern Region of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in the second semester 2019-2020 and in the first semester 2020-2021. The data has been analyzed and the most notable findings could be summarized as follow: The regular classes teachers were devoted to using the UDL principles for teaching and assessing students with learning disabilities. The findings indicated that the most prominent use of regular classes teachers for the UDL principles for teaching and assessing the students with learning disabilities was the second principle: "To provide multiple ways for information presented by the teacher", followed by the first principle: "To provide multiple ways for students to motivate them to learn", and finally the third principle was ranked the last which was: "To provide multiple opportunities for learning and comprehension that meet the students' learning differences". Findings also revealed that there were no statistically significant differences at .05 in the participants' attitudes towards the first principle that could be attributed to gender. However, there were statistically significant differences at .05 that could be attributed to gender in regards to the participants' attitudes towards the first principle, which was for benefit of the female participants. Conversely, the results demonstrated that there were no statistically significant differences at .05 in the participants' attitudes towards the first and the second principles that could be moderated by differences in years experiences. However, there were statistically significant differences at .05 for participants whose experiences were between 5-10 years over those whose experiences were less than 5 years towards the third principle, also showed that there were no statistically significant differences at .05 that could be ascribed to qualification variable. Yet, there were statistically significant differences at .05 among the diploma holders and those who held postgraduate studies degree for the right of diploma holders.</i></p>

Introduction

It is worth noting one of the special education categories is students with learning disabilities. This category is considered a relatively new group, compared to other groups, but it constitutes a large number of individuals that exceeds all special education categories (Ulema and Muhaidat, 2017).

This group is considered one of the special education categories integrated into general education, and students with learning disabilities take a part in general education classrooms, spend a large part of their time inside these classrooms, and receive most of their education from a general education teachers.

Although these students are integrated into general education classrooms, they differ from their ordinary peers in understanding abstract information and speed of processing it, and they often need extra time to complete educational tasks, understand instructions, remember and recall information (Albtal, 2013).

Students with learning disabilities need modern educational designs that are based on a solid framework and have been tested internationally. Therefore, it serves their needs, helps them access the general curriculum, and increases the opportunities for them to integrate into the educational process and benefits from it. Students with learning disabilities need modern educational designs that are based on a solid framework and have been tested

internationally. Universal Design for Learning (UDL) is one of the most prominent modern educational frameworks that considers the variety of students' needs.

The philosophy of UDL is based on providing a flexible learning environment that includes multiple options for acquiring information, whether visual, auditory, or sensory, so it helps students with different needs to maximize their academic achievements. UDL emphasizes the preparation of the core curriculum to address students' variation and then different teaching methods are used to support students' learning (Mahdi, 2017). UDL consists of three principles which are:

The first principles: providing tools for students to stimulate their motivation to learn

The second principles: the provision of tools for presenting information by the teacher

The third principles: Providing learning opportunities that suit individual differences among students (Cast, 2016)

Lit ureal Review

There is a variety of research that uses UDL to determine teachers' knowledge and its effectiveness on students. The following study was applied to know the effect of the UDL in increasing reading comprehension through multimedia. Queenie, Becha, Dalton, Zeff and Smith (2012) selected 16 students. They were divided into three groups, the first group was taught by traditional methods, the second group was taught with only digital books, and the third group was taught with digital books according to the principles of UDL. The results of the study showed that the group who was taught with digital books based on the principles of UDL showed great improvements. The UDL has proven its effectiveness in improving the academic level of students.

There are similar findings of using UDL on students in their academic life. Tzivinkou (2014) examined whether preparing educational materials for undergraduate students under the principles of UDL could help them to access information faster. The study sample consisted of 60 male and female students in the first year of the education college in Greece. Among these students, there were 9 students with learning disabilities. The study tool was a program prepared by the researcher. Also, pre- post test was used. The results revealed that the program helped the students obtain information faster and that university education became easier for them. The program had a positive impact in helping students to increase integration into university education and it improved their ability in decision-making related to their future.

There also multiple studies examined teachers' knowledge of implementing UDL in their classrooms. Curie, Tappe, Siker, and LePage (2013) conducted a study to identify the extent of general education teachers' knowledge and their motivation to apply the UDL, and how they employ these principles in teaching students. The study sample consisted of 45 teachers. The study tool was a design of a training course on how to employ the principles of UDL. The results of the study indicated that teachers have great knowledge and motivation of the principles of UDL and apply them effectively in teaching students.

There is a study that aimed to know the efficiency of teachers who implement UDL. Peace (2016) aimed to increase the teaching efficiency of teachers of deaf and hearing impairment through applying the principles of UDL. The study included the initial perceptions of these teachers toward the UDL as well as the obstacles behind the implementation and application of the UDL. In this study, the researcher used the descriptive approach and the quasi-experimental approach. The study tool consisted of: a questionnaire and design training course based on the response of the questionnaire. The study was split into two phases. The first phase included a survey on 296 teachers of deaf and hearing impairment. In the second phase, 67 male and female teachers took the training course. A measure was used to find out the extent of teachers' familiarity before and after the implementation of the course. The study results showed that there were statistically significant differences between teachers before and after the implementation of the course.

There is a study seeking to know the readiness and the challenges that face general education teachers in applying UDL. Al-Qahtani and Rababaa (2016) investigated the willingness of elementary school teachers in implementing UDL and knowing the difficulties that face teachers when implementing it from their perspective. The study sample included 531 teachers and in the Eastern Province in Saudi Arabia. In the research, the authors used the descriptive approach (survey). The results of the study show that primary school teachers were ready to implement UDL. Furthermore, the authors stated that several obstacles could hinder teachers to implement the UDL which were the lack of preparedness of the environment and school facilities, the ability and the potential of teachers, classroom management and planning for UDL. Also, the study illustrates that there were no statistically significant differences in teachers' willingness to implement UDL due to the gender variable, and there were statistically significant differences attributed to each of (years of experience and specialization).

Research Problem

Students with learning disabilities experience difficulties in keeping pace with general education classes compared to their ordinary peers. Therefore, this affects students with learning disabilities' aspect on psychological, social, and academic levels. As the unsuccessful attempts made by the students to keep up with their peers in the classroom and the recurrence of failure increases the likelihood that they will not be accepted

by their general education teachers and peers, all these support their negative attitudes towards themselves and increases their feelings of frustration and a decline in self-image (Al-Zayat, 1998)

When looking in depth at the situation of students with learning disabilities in regular classrooms, and through the researcher's practical experience, it appears that a large number of this group may be victims of inappropriate teaching methods. Hence, it can cause other educational problems. General education teachers may not consider this category of the students, but they place the responsibility of students' education on special education teachers as if these students are outside their responsibility. And that affects students with learning disabilities on the level of academic and psychological. Therefore, we need to use flexible educational designs that are based on a solid framework and have been tested globally such as UDL, which is one of the most prominent educational frameworks that considers students' needs.

UDL is one of the most suitable educational designs for students with learning disabilities, as experimental and scientific evidence have proven that it meets diverse students according to their characteristics, especially students with learning disabilities, it helps students with needs to progress in general education classrooms.

Research Questions

The research aims to answers the following questions:

To what degree do general education teachers use the principles of UDL in teaching students with learning disabilities?

Are there differences between the general education teachers in applying the principles of UDL in teaching students with learning disabilities due to the variable of gender?

Are there differences between general education teachers in applying the principles of UDL in teaching students with learning disabilities due to the years of experience variable?

Are there differences between general education teachers in applying the principles of UDL in teaching students with learning disabilities due to the qualification variable?

Research Aims:

Identify the degree to which general education teachers use the principles of the universal design of learning in teaching and evaluating students with learning disabilities.

Knowing the impact of the variable (gender - experience - qualification) on general education teachers in implementing the principles of universal design in teaching and evaluating students with learning disabilities.

Method

Research Sample

The study sample consisted of 500 general education teachers working in elementary school in public education in the Eastern Region. Those teachers teach students with learning disabilities who enrolled in resource rooms part-time and then take part in the mainstream classes

Research Tools

A questionnaire measuring the principles of UDL in the methods of teaching students with learning disabilities. The questionnaire consists of three sections and each section compromises 33 items.

The first section: providing tools for students to stimulate their motivation to learn

The second section: the provision of tools for presenting information by the teacher

The third section: providing learning opportunities that suit individual differences among students

The Psychometric Properties of The Tool

Validate Tool Internal Consistency

In order to verify the validity of the internal consistency of the questioners, Pearson's Correlation Coefficient was calculated. Therefore, the authors can find out the degree to which each of the questionnaire statements is related to the overall score of the axis.

Table (1) Pearson correlation coefficients of the first axis statement with the total score of the axis

The extent to which general education teachers use the principles of universal design for learning in teaching and evaluating students with learning difficulties

Section	Item number	Correlation Coefficient	Item number	Correlation Coefficient
The first principle: providing tools for students to stimulate their motivation to learn	1	0.580**	6	0.600**
	2	0.629**	7	0.693**
	3	0.679**	8	0.702**
	4	0.585**	9	0.677**
	5	0.562**	-	-
The second principle: the	10	0.609**	16	0.664**

provision of tools for	11	0.581**	17	0.671**
presenting information by the	12	0.600**	18	0.639**
teacher	13	0.591**	19	0.696**
	14	0.678**	20	0.640**
	15	0.623**	21	0.637**
	22	0.675**	28	0.675**
The third principle:	23	0.674**	29	0.711**
Providing learning	24	0.694**	30	0.674**
opportunities that suit	25	0.671**	31	0.646**
individual differences among	26	0.694**	32	0.638**
students	27	0.597**	33	0.528**

* D at the **ificance** level 0.01 or less

As it can be seen from Table (1) that the values of the correlation coefficient of each of the statements with its axis are positive. Also, statistical function at the level of significance (0.01) or less indicates the validity of the internal consistency between the statements of the first axis, and their relevance to measuring what they were prepared to measure.

The Validity of The Tool

The reliability of the search tool was confirmed by (Cronbach's alpha equation). It showed that the questioner is highly reliable and it could be applied.

Results

The answer to the first question: What is the degree to which teachers in regular classes use the principles of UDL in teaching and evaluating students with learning disabilities?

To determine the degree to which teachers in regular classes use the principles of UDL in teaching and evaluating students with learning disabilities, the arithmetic mean of these dimensions was calculated, Table (2) illustrates the results:

Table (2) the responses of research sample on the degree to which general education teachers use the principles of universal design for learning in teaching students with learning disabilities

section	Arithmetic mean	standard deviation	Rank
1 Providing tools for students to stimulate their motivation to learn	2.67	0.320	2
2 The provision of tools for presenting information by the teacher	2.69	0.318	1
3 Providing learning opportunities that suit individual differences among students	2.64	0.350	3
The extent to which general education teachers use the principles of universal design for learning in teaching and evaluating students with learning difficulties	2.67	0.300	-

The results show that teachers in regular classes use the principles of UDL in teaching students with learning disabilities with an average of (2.67 out of 3). The most principle used by teachers is that providing multiple tools of representation (2.69 out of 3), followed by providing multiple tools for students to stimulate their motivation to learn and engage with an average (2.67 out of 3). Finally, the third principle was providing multiple opportunities to express students' understanding (2.64 out of 3).

The results infer that the high responses to the second principle because teachers were willing to deliver information to all students of different abilities by presenting the lesson in a variety of ways, implementing

multiple strategies to present the information, as well as using audio, visual and sensory means. That indicates teachers of regular classes feel responsible towards students with learning difficulties.

The research also attributes the high responses to the second principle specifically among the three principles to that teachers are eager to make efforts in preparing the tools that related to the presentation of the lesson and how to simplify the information to the students. Also, teachers give this part of the class the greatest attention, compared to their interest in the first and the third principles. This result is similar to the result of Cory et al. (2013); which indicated the teachers have great knowledge and motivation of the principles of UDL and how to implement these principles effectively in teaching students.

The answer to the second question: are there differences between the general education classroom teachers in using the principles of UDL to teach students with learning disabilities due to the variable of gender?

To identify whether there are statistically significant differences in the responses of the study members according to the difference in the sex variable, the Independent Sample T-test was used to clarify the significance of the differences between the responses of the study individuals and the results represent in Table (3):

Table (3) the results of the "Independent Sample T-test" for the differences between the responses s according to the gender variable.

Section	Gender	number	Mean	standard deviation	T-test	Significance	Comment
providing tools for students to stimulate their motivation to learn	Male	230	2.64	0.307	-1.760	0.079	Non-function
	Female	270	2.69	0.330			
Provision of tools for presenting information by the teacher	Male	230	2.65	0.273	-2.515	0.012*	function
	Female	270	2.72	0.349			
Providing learning opportunities that suit individual differences among students	Male	230	2.60	0.330	-2.676	0.008**	function
	Female	270	2.68	0.362			
The extent to which general education teachers use the principles of universal design for learning in teaching and evaluating students with learning difficulties	Male	230	2.63	0.266	-2.624	0.009**	function
	Female	270	2.70	0.323			

** A function at the level of 0.01 or less * a function at the level of 0.05 or less

The results show that there are statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05) or less in the research sample. Female teachers are more likely to apply the second Principle. The results also demonstrate that there are statistically significant differences at the level (0.01) and less in the attitudes of male and female teachers. The female teachers are more likely to implement the third principle and the degree of use of general education classroom teachers in teaching and evaluating students with learning difficulties. The results of this research differ from the results Al-Qahtani (2019) study, the results of Al-Qahtani (2019) showed that there were no statistically significant differences at the level of significance (0.05) or less in the willingness of general education teachers to implement UDL in teaching. However, The results of this current study are consistent with Al-Toubasi (2019) which indicated that there are statistically significant differences in the level of knowledge of general education teachers; Female teachers are more knowledgeable, The research attributes this result to the fact that females tend to prepare various and innovative educational aids.

The answer to the third question: are there differences between general education teachers in using the principles of UDL in the teaching and evaluation of students with learning disabilities due to the variable of

years of experience? In order to identify whether there were statistically significant differences in the responses, ANOVA was used. The results illustrate in Table(4).

Table (4) Results of "One Way ANOVA" for differences in responses of study sample according to the years of experience variable

Section	Source of Variance	Sum of squares	degrees of freedom	Mean squares	F Calculated	Significance	Comments
providing tools for students to stimulate their motivation to learn	Between Groups	0.388	2	0.194	1.895	0.151	Non-function
	Within Groups	50.817	497	0.102			
	Total	51.205	499	-			
the provision of tools for presenting information by the teacher	Between Groups	0.282	2	0.141	1.397	0.248	Non-function
	Within Groups	50.147	497	0.101			
	total	50.429	499	-			
Providing learning opportunities that suit individual differences among students	Between Groups	1.296	2	0.648	5.381	0.005**	function
	Within Groups	59.866	497	0.120			
	total	61.162	499	-			
The extent to which general education teachers use the principles of universal design for learning in teaching and evaluating students with learning difficulties	Between Groups	0.594	2	0.297	3.340	0.036*	function
	Within Groups	44.177	497	0.089			
	total	44.771	499	-			

** A function at the level of 0.01 and less * a function at the level of 0.05 and less

Table (4) represents that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05) or less in the attitudes of the research sample on the first and second principles according to the differences in the years of experience variable. Table (4) shows that there are statistically significant differences at the level of (0.01) and less in the attitudes of the research sample on the third principle according to the difference in the years of experience variable. In term of the variable of years of experience, it is shown in Table (4) that there are statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05) or less in the attitudes of the research sample about (the degree to which teachers of regular classes use the principles of UDL in teaching students with learning disabilities). To determine the differences between the categories of years of experience, Scheffe' Test was used. The results appear in Table (5) :

Table (5) shows the results of Scheffe' Test to verify the differences between the categories of years of experience

Axis	years of experience	number	Arithmetic mean	Less than 5 years	From 5 to 10 years	More than 10 years
Providing learning opportunities that suit individual differences among students	Less than 5 years	75	2.52	-	*	**
	From 5 to 10 years	146	2.65		-	
	More than 10 years	279	2.67			-
The extent to which general education teachers use the principles of universal design for learning in teaching and evaluating students with learning difficulties	Less than 5 years	75	2.59	-		*
	From 5 to 10 years	146	2.67		-	
	More than 10 years	279	2.69			-

Table (5) demonstrates that there are statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05) and less between general education teachers whose years of experience are less than 5 years and general education teachers whose years of experience from 5-10 years in applying the third principle. Research participants whose years of

experience are from 5 to 10 years are more likely to apply this principle in their class. Also, Table (5) shows that there are statistically significant differences at the level of (0.01) or less between general education teachers whose years of experience are less than 5 years and general education teachers with 10 years experience or more in implementing the third Principle, general education teachers who have 10 years experiences or more are more likely to implement this principle. Table (5) illustrates that there are statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05) or less between general education teachers whose years of experience are less than 5 years and general education teachers with 10 years of experience or more in term of (the extent to which teachers of regular classes use the principles of UDL in teaching and evaluation of students with learning disabilities). General education teachers who have more than 10 years of experience are more likely to use this principle. This result is consistent with the study that conducted by Sartawi and Qaraqish (2016), whose results showed that there are statistically significant differences at the level of significance 0,05) regarding self-efficacy of general education teachers in teaching students with learning disabilities who have 10 years of experience. However, this result is contrary to the study conducted by Al-Toubasi (2019), In Al-Toubasi (2019) the results indicated that there were no statistically significant differences between new and experienced teachers in terms of preparation to implement classroom adjustments and adaptations for students with learning disabilities. The answer to the fourth question: are there differences between the general education teachers in using the principles of UDL in teaching students with learning disabilities due to the qualification variable? In order to determine whether there were statistically significant differences in the responses One Way ANOVA was used. To clarify the significance of these differences, the results were as shown in the following table:

Table (6) the results of "One Way ANOVA" for the differences in the responses of study individuals according to the difference in the qualification variable.

Axis	Source of Variance	Mean squares	degrees of freedom	Mean squares	F Calculated	Significance	Comment
providing tools for students to stimulate their motivation to learn	Between Groups	0.267	2	0.134	1.303	0.273	Non-function
	Within Groups	50.938	497	0.102			
	Total	51.205	499	-			
the provision of tools for presenting information by the teacher	Between Groups	0.345	2	0.172	1.712	0.182	Non-function
	Within Groups	50.084	497	0.101			
	Total	50.429	499	-			
Providing learning opportunities that suit individual differences among students	Between Groups	0.906	2	0.453	3.735	0.025*	function
	Within Groups	60.257	497	0.121			
	Total	61.162	499	-			
The extent to which general education teachers use the principles of universal design for learning in teaching and evaluating students with learning difficulties	Between Groups	0.484	2	0.242	2.717	0.067	Non-function
	Within Groups	44.287	497	0.089			
	Total	44.771	499	-			

* A function at the level of 0.05 or less

It appears in Table (6) that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05) or less in the attitudes of research individuals in applying the three principles in terms of the qualification variable. The results in Table (6) show that there are statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05) and less in the general education teachers' attitudes toward the third principle: in term of qualification variable. To determine the differences between the qualification categories Scheffe' Test was used, the results represent in Table (7):

Table (7) shows the results of the Scheffe' Test to verify the differences between the qualification categories

	Axis	qualification	Number	Arithmetic mean	diploma	Bachelor	Postgraduate
Providing learning opportunities that suit individual differences among students		diploma	58	2.70	-		*
		Bachelor	408	2.65		-	
		Postgraduate	34	2.50			-

Table (7) shows that there are statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05) or less between general education teachers who have a diploma qualification and general education teachers who hold bachelor or postgraduate degrees in the third principle. The research interprets this difference to the fact that teachers who have a diploma qualification are the oldest teachers with high educational experience who have been hired for their diploma. Thus they have sufficient experience to deal with students with learning disabilities. This result is unlike the study was conducted by Al-Muzairi (2019) In Al-muzairi (2019) the results showed there were significant differences at the level of significance (0.05) or less about teachers' expectations towards UDL in favor of those who hold BA.

Conclusion

The current research aimed at identifying the degree to which general education teachers use the principles of comprehensive design for learning in teaching and evaluating students with learning difficulties according to the variable (gender - experience - qualification). After analyzing the data statistically, the research reached several results. The most important is that regular classroom teachers use the principles of a comprehensive design for learning in teaching and evaluating students with learning difficulties. Also, it became clear from the results that the most prominent principles used by general education teachers is the second principle, followed by the first principle, and finally, the third principle came.

Recommendations

Based on the results, the researchers recommend the following:

- General education teachers should have a training course on teaching skills that help students with learning disabilities to access the general curriculum.
- Encourage general education teachers to teach students with learning disabilities how to use self-evaluation skills.
- Direct general education teachers to allow students with learning disabilities to choose activities that suit their interests.
- Encourage general education teachers to teach students with learning disabilities how to use strategies that help them quickly gain and retain information.
- Direct general education teachers on how to use educational aids that can be suitable for students with learning disabilities.
- Direct general education teachers to provide multiple opportunities for students with learning disabilities to express their understanding, such as offering an assistant teacher who writes the answers for students who experience writing difficulties during the test.
- Encourage general education teachers to provide assignments and homework that suit students with learning difficulties abilities.

Acknowledgements or Notes

Please collate acknowledgements or notes in a separate section at the end of the article before the references.

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